

Deep hydrothermal system experiments

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
SoA	State of the Art
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

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1. Introduction

The present document reports on the field test which took place in the last reporting period of the RAMONES project (M37-M48). In addition to partial testing of the instrument the document includes the details of the final field testing inside the crater of the submarine volcano Kolumbo off Santorini Island, where an active hydrothermal vent field exists. In addition, complete testing of the full fleet of instruments took place in Santorini caldera. Details of the various individual and collaborative missions are described.

2. The hydrothermal system in Kolumbo, Santorini

Kolumbo is an active submarine volcano located approximately 7 km northeast of Santorini Island in Greece and serves as a pertinent case for the deep hydrothermal system experiments of the RAMONES project. Its historical record includes an eruption in 1650 CE that produced a catastrophic tsunami and casualties from noxious gases in Santorini. Eyewitness accounts mention maximum water run-up heights of 20 m on the southern coast of Ios, inundation of an area of 240 m inland on Sikinos, and a flooding of up to 2 km² inland on the eastern coast of Santorini. Recent studies suggest that a potential future eruption of Kolumbo poses a substantial hazard to the northern and eastern coasts of Santorini.

Kolumbo crater floor is covered by Fe-rich microbial mats and Fe-oxyhydroxide deposits, with temperatures ranging from 16.2°C to 17°C. Low-temperature fluids ($\leq 70^\circ\text{C}$) and CO₂ bubbles emerge from these mats, potentially supporting microbial productivity. The seawater column above 250 m includes Fe-rich particles, while white microbial mats colonize the northern crater wall (~490 m) at fluid seep sites.

In 2006, Remotely Operated Vehicle explorations in the northern part of Kolumbo's crater floor revealed an extensive "diffuse-flow"-style hydrothermal vent field, Kolumbo Hydrothermal Field (KHF), between 492 and 504 m depth. In 2010 and 2011, onboard E/V Nautilus, a bathymetric map of KHF was created by utilizing the 1,375 kHz BlueView multibeam sonar, structured light and stereo imagery data acquired by the ROV Hercules. The detailed swath bathymetric mapping using 0.5 m grid interval revealed an extensive field with numerous active vents in the central part of KHF, with larger but less active vents occurring in the northern part of the crater floor.

The Kolumbo Hydrothermal Field (KHF) consists of sulphide-sulphate spires, mounds, and flanges along a NE-SW trend. The Politeia Vent Complex features short (≤ 3 m) sulphide-sulphate spires, which discharge clear shimmering fluids, unlike black smokers. These spires, covered by microbial biofilms, resemble vents in the SW Pacific and Mid-Atlantic Ridge.

The Champagne and Diffuser II Vent Complexes consist of Fe-rich microbial mounds, emitting CO₂ bubbles, leading to acidic (pH ~ 5) and CO₂-stratified waters, which may cause local oxygen depletion. The highest vent temperature recorded (2010) was 210°C, with the largest Fe microbial vent, Poet's Candle (~4 m tall), on the northern crater slope.

3. Surveys of the gliders in the underwater area of Kolumbo volcano

The mapping of natural radioactivity in the underwater hydrothermal vent of Kolumbo, located near the island of Santorini, is one of the primary objectives of the project. Over the years, the geological and physiochemical characteristics of Kolumbo have been extensively studied, and the volcano is continuously monitored using specialized instruments. However, the presence and distribution of natural radioactivity in Kolumbo have received less attention, primarily due to the challenges associated with underwater radioactivity mapping and monitoring, challenges that this project aims to overcome.

To address this, the RAMONES team organized an expedition to Kolumbo with the goal of deploying the RAMONES gliders, equipped with the γ Sniffer instrument, inside the volcano's crater to map gamma radioactivity levels. Additionally, the gliders were fitted with an integrated CTD sensor, allowing for simultaneous collection of conductivity, temperature, and depth data, which provide valuable context for interpreting the radioactivity measurements.

The deployment was conducted as part of the final RAMONES integration field tests, with the research team operating at Kolumbo on October 26th and 27th. A catamaran served as the surface vessel and operational base, supporting the deployment and navigation of the gliders throughout the expedition.

3.1. Participants

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	Antonio C. Domínguez Brito

3.2. Experiments Setup

The field experiments at Kolumbo were conducted using the RAMONES glider of NTUA. The NTUA glider was fitted with the following instruments:

1. γ Sniffer for gamma radioactivity measurements,
2. CTD sensor for collecting conductivity, temperature, and depth data,
3. Acoustic modems (EvoLogics USBL) for underwater tracking and real-time communication with a surface vessel.

A catamaran (Figure 1) served as the operational base, supporting the deployment, navigation, and recovery of the glider. The EvoLogics top-side USBL modem was deployed from the catamaran, to achieve acoustic communication with the glider vehicle. Moreover, a dedicated GNSS receiver was fitted on the vessel, providing the position of the boat, which is considered in the NTUA glider positioning stack for estimating the position of the glider in the water. The control of the glider, the visualisation of the boat and glider positions and the handling of the data transmitted by the glider via the acoustic channel and via the joint RF/WiFi connection to the glider when on the surface, were handled by dedicated laptop computers on the catamaran.

Figure 1 – A Catamaran was used as an operational base for the glider operations at Kolumbo on Oct 26th and 27th.

3.3. Measurements with the γ -Sniffers

Underwater operations were performed with the μ SPEC4000 CZT-based sensor (SN:278) aboard the autonomous underwater glider in the area of the submarine volcano Kolumbo. The sensor was enclosed in an aluminum housing of 2 mm thickness. Table 1 presents all the sensor's parameters adopted during the operations.

Table 1 - Parameters utilized for the operation of the μ SPEC4000 CZT-based sensor (SN: 278)

Parameter	Value
High voltage (V)	1500
Number of channels	4096
LLD (ch)	32
ULD (ch)	4095
Coarse gain	5
Fine gain	1.0925

A critical decision was made on the operational principle of the γ -Sniffer. It was found that the acquisition of independent files for each measurement resulted in long, non-measuring time windows. These 'dead' time windows were attributed to the start-stop-clear stage of the ROS-based algorithm responsible for the data acquisition of the sensor when operating aboard the glider. In order to treat this problem, a cumulative operation mode scheme was utilized, where the detector was measuring non-stop. However, every 10 seconds, everything measured from the beginning of the deployment was written on a separate file. Therefore, every spectrum obtained includes information for the last 10 seconds AND all previous spectra. To obtain dedicated CPS measurements, automated subtraction ($i(n+1)-i(n)$) of the total counts registered was performed to provide the counts of each individual time interval.

The first deployment took place on the 26th of October 2024 and 1386 measurements of 10 s each, were performed throughout the survey. Figure 2 represents the data collected, in the form of a time series for the total count rate (integration of the full energy spectrum) variation.

Via correlation of the total CPS detected from the sensor against the depth in the water during the motion of the underwater glider, a certain pattern can be observed. As the glider approaches the seabed, an increase of the total CPS occurs (see CPS variation at 12:00 pm in Figure 3).

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Figure 2 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 26/10/2024

Figure 3 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 26/10/2024 (including information on the depth of the measurement)

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The second deployment took place on the 27th of October 2024 and 2502 measurements of 10 s each, were performed throughout the survey. Figure 3 represents all the data collected, in the form of a time series for the total count rate (integration of the full energy spectrum) variation.

Figure 4 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 27/10/2024

As stated above, the total CPS were correlated with the deployment depth of the glider. Similarly to the first survey, a rise in the CPS registered is exhibited when the glider gets closer to the seabed surface (see Figures Figure 5Figure 6Figure 7).

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Figure 5 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 27/10/2024 (including information on the depth of the measurement)

Figure 6 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 27/10/2024 for the first dive (including information on the depth of the measurement)

Figure 7 - Time Series of the total CPS registered during the maneuvers of the glider in Kolumbo at 27/10/2024 for the second dive (including information on the depth of the measurement)

3.4. Operations and results

3.4.1. Experiments at Kolumbo on 26/10/2024

On the first day, a series of test missions were conducted to gradually evaluate the performance of the glider at different depths and validate its overall functionality. These missions focused on verifying system stability, assessing movement characteristics such as descent and ascent behaviour, and ensuring proper operation of onboard sensors and communication systems.

Missions 2, 4, and 6 were primarily navigational, as the glider did not always surface exactly where expected due to currents and other environmental factors. After each completed mission, a new mission was initiated to direct the glider to a designated waypoint located above an active area of Kolumbo. This waypoint served as the starting position for all subsequent missions, ensuring consistency in the deployment and execution of the tests.

Throughout the day, the glider was tested in progressively deeper dives, with each mission contributing to the overall assessment of its operational capabilities. The final mission (7) focused on testing the backseat driver functionality, which enabled real-time adjustments to various mission parameters using pre-programmed commands.

In these missions, the pinger/replier control and communications stack described in detail in D2.3 has been tested. The stack features the developed ROS nodes for reading and writing glider navigation variables through the backseat driver and for receiving commands using the acoustic communications. By sending instructions via the acoustic modem and processing with the backseat driver, we could actively modify glider navigation parameters during the mission. Additionally, mission-critical real-time data from the glider were fetched via the

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backseat driver and the gsniffer handled by the auxiliary RPi4 single-board computer installed in the glider, and they were transmitted back to the surface vehicle using piggyback messages supported by the EvoLogics hardware. These data included vacuum status, leak detection alerts, and key navigation variables such as depth rate and actual depth measured by onboard sensors, offering a more reliable reference than USBL positioning, which may introduce localization errors.

Table 2 - Summary of missions performed on October 26th.

Mission number	Designated Depth (m)	Trajectory type
1	40	Spiral/helix
2	30	Yos to waypoint
3	200	Spiral/helix
4	30	Yos to waypoint
5	400	Spiral/helix
6	30	Yos to waypoint
7	20-7-20	Spiral/helix

Below, we present a selection of plots primarily from the 400 m depth mission, as the key operational parameters remained consistent across all dives, with the only variation being the target depth. Some of the most important parameters include the pitch angle, which was set to 15 degrees during descent and ascent, directly affecting the glider's vertical speed (0.25 m/s average descent, 0.20 m/s average ascent, due to the ballast configuration). The predefined minimum depth rate was ± 0.2 m/s. If this speed was not matched by the buoyancy pump by itself, the thruster was utilized. Additionally, the fin tail angle was maintained at 25 degrees, enabling the glider's helicoidal motion with an approximate turning radius of 10 meters. The glider performed 11 spirals during descent and 17 during ascent due to the difference in vertical speed.

Figure 8 displays a 3D plot of the glider's trajectory based on dead reckoning, overlaid with positioning data obtained from the USBL system. In the plot, the trajectory line starts in blue and gradually transitions to yellow over time, representing the progression of the glider's movement throughout the mission. There are noticeable differences between the dead reckoning and USBL positioning, with USBL showing significant errors at shallow depths while generally being more reliable than dead reckoning, as it is not affected by cumulative drift errors and sensor inaccuracies over time. Furthermore, the calculation of the position through dead reckoning, cannot take into account drifts due to currents or other external factors, as the glider is not equipped with the appropriate sensors to directly measure its position while underwater. Meanwhile, Figure 9 presents the CTD sensor data collected during the missions. Notably, the thermocline begins at approximately 50 m depth and stabilizes at approximately 150 m, marking a significant change in water column properties.

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Figure 8 - 3D trajectory of glider based on dead-reckoning and USBL data for the 5th mission (400 m dive) of October 26th.

Figure 9 - CTD plots from the fifth mission on Oct. 26th, reporting water temperature (left), salinity (middle) and density (right).

3.4.1.1. Details on mission 3 (200 m depth, helical)

During Mission 3, the glider followed a helical descent pattern, reaching a target depth of 200 m. The primary trajectory of the glider, as measured by the USBL system, is shown in Figure 11. However, adverse weather conditions caused significant movement of the catamaran, disrupting the communication with the USBL and affecting localization accuracy.

Figures Figure 10Figure 11 provide key insights into the mission. Figure 11 illustrates the depth variations of the glider over time, as estimated by the USBL, alongside the corresponding counts per second (CPS) measured by the gSniffer instrument. The observed fluctuations in climb and descent rates are likely due to variations in hydrodynamic drag and differences in the glider's vertical speed during ascent and descent. Since the integration time of the γ Sniffer remains constant, this speed variation could explain minor differences in CPS readings.

Regarding the CPS measurements, the data remain relatively stable throughout the mission, with a slight upward trend during ascent. Figure 12 shows the CPS distribution across different depths, generally appearing uniform. However, a distinct anomaly is observed at approximately 130 m, indicating a higher concentration of radioactive material, possibly associated with the layering of the water column inside the Kolumbo crater, as a variation to the CTD values can also be observed at this depth.

Figure 10 - Kolumbo underwater volcano bathymetry with Points of Interest

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Figure 11 - Glider trajectories in Kolumbo's Dynamic Hydrothermal Field

Figure 12 - γ Sniffer CPS from spiral dive at 200 m target depth on October 26th (red), depth change (blue)

Figure 13 - γ Sniffer CPS distribution from spiral dive at 200 m target depth on October 26th

3.4.1.2. Details on mission 5 (400 metre depth, helical)

Figure 14 presents the γ Sniffer CPS data collected during the spiral dive to a target depth of 400 m on October 26th. The red line represents CPS values over time, while the blue line shows depth variation (Z) throughout the dive. Overall, the CPS measurements remain stable during both descent and ascent, with only minor fluctuations. The most significant variations are observed in the depth rate. The change was performed by using the pinger/replier control and communication stack, requesting an increase in the depth rate of the glider.

The scatter plot in Figure 15 illustrates the relationship between CPS and depth. While the CPS distribution appears generally uniform across depths, a distinct anomaly is once again observed at approximately 130 m. This matches the anomaly detected during the 200-m dive, corroborating that a higher concentration was indeed present at this location.

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Figure 14 - γ Sniffer CPS from spiral dive at 400 m target depth on October 26th (red), depth change (blue).

Figure 15 - γ Sniffer CPS distribution from spiral dive at 400 m target depth on October 26th.

3.4.1.3. Experiments with Backseat Driver

The final mission of the day consisted of two yo-yo maneuvers at a depth of 20 m and a climb depth of 7 m. The primary objective was to ensure that we were successfully receiving safety-related measurements from the glider via the piggyback messages, including vacuum status, leak detection as well as gamma radiation counts from the γ Sniffer. Additionally, this mission allowed us to actively modify mission parameters during execution, by sending specialized messages via the acoustic modem. Initially, the target depth was set to 20 m, but a command was sent via the acoustic modem to adjust it to 30 m, demonstrating the capability to dynamically control the glider's operations in real time. The command to change the target depth was sent early (when the glider was approximately 5-10 m deep) as we needed to ensure that communications through the acoustic modem would not be lost.

3.4.2. Experiments at Kolumbo on 27/10/2024

On the second day, three missions were conducted (Table 3) to gather the necessary data. Mission 2 was primarily navigational, ensuring that the glider reached the designated region of interest, as strong currents and weather conditions frequently displaced it from its intended path.

Missions 1 and 3 were the most critical dives, during which the glider descended near the bottom of Kolumbo's crater to collect both radioactivity (CPS) and CTD data. The backseat driver functionality was actively used in both dives, allowing real-time adjustments to key mission parameters. This ensured precise control over the glider's trajectory and optimized data collection throughout the mission.

Table 3 - Mission performed on the 27th of October overview.

Mission number	Designated Depth (m)	Trajectory type
1	420	Spiral/helix
2	30	Yo to waypoint
3	465-100-465	Spiral/helix

Below, we present a selection of plots primarily from the 465-100-465 m mission, where the glider followed a helicoidal trajectory in a distinctive 'W' depth pattern. Key operational parameters remained consistent with previous day missions, including a pitch angle of 25 degrees during descent and 15 degrees during ascent, as well as a fin tail angle of 25 degrees. Note that during Mission 1, targeting a depth of 420 m, the minimum ascent depth rate was set to 0.8 m/s with a pitch angle of 10 degrees. This configuration resulted in an early mission abort, as the thruster was unable to generate enough thrust to achieve the required ascent speed at such a low pitch angle.

Figure 16 - Reconstructed 3D trajectories of the glider based on USBL and dead-reckoning data for the 3rd mission performed on Oct. 27th. presents a 3D plot of the glider's trajectory based on dead reckoning, overlaid with positioning data from the USBL system. Notably, the dead reckoned trajectory appears to drift eastward, while the USBL positioning suggests a movement toward the west. This discrepancy can be explained by the initial GPS reading of the glider, which shifts eastward before the dive begins. As a result, the dead reckoning system incorrectly assumes an eastward water velocity. However, as the glider descends, it becomes evident that this assumption does not hold, leading to the observed divergence between the two positioning methods. Figure 17 presents the CTD sensor data collected during the mission,

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showing similar trends to previous dives. The thermocline remains practically the same, starting at approximately the same depth as observed in prior missions from the first day (Oct. 26th).

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Figure 16 - Reconstructed 3D trajectories of the glider based on USBL and dead-reckoning data for the 3rd mission performed on Oct. 27th.

Figure 17 - CTD plots from the third mission on Oct. 27th, 2024, reporting water temperature (left), salinity (middle) and density (right)

3.4.2.1. Details on mission 1 (420 m depth, helical)

The γ Sniffer CPS data collected during a helix dive to a target depth of 420 m on October 27th is presented in the figures below. The time-series plot (Figure 18) illustrates the depth variations recorded by the USBL system (blue line) alongside the CPS measurements from the γ Sniffer instrument (red line) over time. In this figure the early abort can be clearly noticed at 8000 (timestamp) where the depth rate suddenly increases. As the glider descended and ascended, fluctuations in CPS values were observed, with higher counts detected near the bottom. These variations may indicate changes in gamma radiation levels, possibly due to the hydrothermal activity within the Kolumbo crater.

The scatter plot (Figure 19) visualizes the CPS distribution across different depths, with the Z-coordinate representing depth and the colour scale indicating CPS values. Overall, the data show a relatively uniform distribution, with occasional spikes, particularly at greater depths, which may suggest specific points of interest within the crater.

Figure 18 - γ Sniffer CPS from spiral dive at 420 m target depth on October 27th (red), depth change (blue).

Figure 19 - γ Sniffer CPS distribution from spiral dive at 420 m target depth on October 27th.

3.4.2.2. Details on mission 3 (465-100-465 metre depth, helical)

The γ Sniffer CPS data from the final and most critical dive, targeting a depth of 465 m (465-100-465), conducted on October 27th, is presented in the figures below.

The time-series plot (

Figure 20) illustrates the depth variations recorded by the USBL system (blue line) alongside the CPS measurements from the γ Sniffer instrument (red line) throughout the dive. CPS fluctuations were observed during both descent and ascent, with consistent readings and distinct peaks at specific depths. These peaks suggest localized variations in gamma radiation levels, likely linked to unique geological or environmental features within the Kolumbo crater.

The scatter plot (

Figure 21) provides a detailed representation of CPS distribution across different depths. While lower and moderate CPS values appear evenly distributed, distinct peaks are clearly visible. The first notable peak occurs around 150 meters, while the most prominent and consistent peaks are observed at depths below 400 meters, with the highest CPS readings recorded near the crater floor. These findings indicate increased gamma radiation levels near the bottom of Kolumbo, highlighting key areas of geological interest.

Figures Figure 22 and

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Figure 23, shows the radioactivity distribution reconstruction based on the measurements collected inside the Kolumbo using the ENEGMa method, described in D4.3 and D4.4. The figure shows the activity in terms of counts-per-second as measured by the γ Sniffer, both on the trajectory as well as in its immediate vicinity. The considerations made above, regarding higher observed activity near the bottom (hydrothermal field) and in the layer between 200 and 100 m are also evident in these plots.

Figure 20 - γ Sniffer CPS from spiral dive at 465 (465-100-465) m target depth on October 27th (red), depth change (blue).

Figure 21 - γ Sniffer CPS distribution from spiral dive at (465-100-465) m target depth on October 27th.

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Figure 22 - 3D plot of radioactivity distribution on the glider trajectory from the helicoidal dive during the 3rd (465-100-465 m) mission on October 27th.

Figure 23 - 3D plot of radioactivity distribution in the immediate vicinity around the glider trajectory from the helicoidal dive during the 3rd (465-100-465 m) mission on October 27th.

3.4.2.3. Experiments with Backseat Driver

During the 465-100-465 m mission on the second day, we utilized the backseat driver functionality through the pinger/replier control and communications stack to dynamically adjust the pitch angle during ascent at specific points, as shown in Figure 24 (red circles). The plot illustrates these changes, with the measured pitch (in radians) represented in blue, the commanded pitch in orange and the measured depth rate (in m/s), which is directly affected by the pitch angle changes, in green. In addition to modifying mission parameters in real time, we were also receiving continuous feedback from the glider, allowing us to monitor critical status information such as vacuum levels, leak detection, battery level and depth readings. This real-time data exchange ensured that the glider was operating safely and effectively while enabling precise control over its ascent profile.

Figure 24 - Changes in glider navigation command parameters (in orange) performed via the Backseat driver and the resulting changes in directly (pitch) and indirectly (depth rate) affected measured quantities

Some images from the Kolumbo expedition are shown below.

Deep hydrothermal system experiments

Deep hydrothermal system experiments

4. Deployment of the benthic laboratory

4.1. Deployment area

The measurement location was Nea Kameni hot springs (see Figure 25).

Figure 25 - Maps illustrating the deployment location of the benthic lab

4.2. Participants

Partner	Name
PLOATECH	Angelos Mallios
	Othonas Vlassopoulos
	Enrique Fernadez
	Richard Camilli
NTUA	Valsamis Ntouskos
NKUA	Theo Mertzimekis
	Georgios Siltzovalis

4.3. Imaging instruments - SUGI and CHERI

Both SUGI and CHERI instruments have been deployed in Nea Kammeni, mounted on the benthic lab. The tests aimed to ensure the correct operation of the instruments on the benthic lab, the ability of the benthic processing units and network infrastructure to handle the data flow from all the instruments mounted on the benthic lab. As the deployment was on coastal zone and performed during the day, the tests did not target Cherenkov radiation detection. Nevertheless, data streams have been acquired from both SUGI and CHERI instruments to confirm their correct operation. Figure 26 shows both CHERI instruments mounted on the benthic lab, during the operations at Santorini in October 2024. Figure 27 and Figure 28 show sample data captured by the SUGI and CHERI instruments, respectively, during the dive at Nea Kammeni on November 1st.

Deep hydrothermal system experiments

Figure 26 - SUGI (bottom left) and CHERI instruments (bottom right and top right) mounted on the benthic lab.

Figure 27 - Spectrum and pixel activations from the events collected by the SUGI instrument during the deployment of the Benthic Lab at Nea Kammeni.

Figure 28 - Images captured using the CHERI-SPC (left) and CHERI-UV (right) instruments during the test of Benthic Lab at Nea Kameni

4.4. γ Sniffer and correlation with the CTD data

The μ SPEC4000 CZT-based sensor (SN:277) was deployed in Santorini's caldera as part of the instrumentation mounted onto the benthic laboratory (see Figure 29). Measurements, implementing data acquisition of short time intervals, were performed at two different depths in the seawater.

Figure 29 - The μ SPEC4000 CZT-based sensor mounted onto the benthic lab

Table 4 - Parameters utilized for the operation of the μ SPEC4000 CZT-based sensor (SN: 277)

Parameter	Value
High voltage (V)	1400
Number of channels	4096
LLD (ch)	32
ULD (ch)	4095
Coarse gain	5
Fine gain	1.1

Additionally, a CTD sensor (AML-3 XC manufactured by AML oceanographic) was also mounted on the benthic lab (see Figure 30) providing measurements (after every 2 s) of temperature, conductivity, depth, pressure and salinity of the seawater (see Figure 31 - Figure 34). These parameters were correlated with the data gathered with the CZT-based sensor.

Figure 30 - The CTD sensor mounted onto the benthic lab

Figure 31 - Seawater's temperature against the deployment depth of the benthic laboratory

Figure 32 - Seawater's salinity against the deployment depth of the benthic laboratory

Figure 33 - Seawater's conductivity against the deployment depth of the benthic laboratory

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Figure 34 - Data collected from the CTD sensor in the form of time series

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The sensor registered events for two different depths in the water column. The first one was at 11 m, while the latter at 16 m from the surface of the sea. The count rate registered, increased at the larger deployment depth implying a stronger contribution of radioactivity emitted by the seabed (see Figure 35). Another parameter that could have affected the measurement, is the salinity of the seawater (26.4% deviation between the two values of salinity). Studies have shown that there is a direct correlation between the salinity and the concentration of ^{40}K in the seawater. The statistics accumulated in both cases were not sufficient to perform spectroscopy and thus, only the variation of the count rate could be examined.

Figure 35 - Total CPS registered during the measurements at two different depths, with the $\mu\text{SPEC4000}$ (#277) on the benthic lab along with the mean values of selected physical parameters of the seawater as extracted from the CTD sensor (log-log scale)

4.5. GASPAR

Moreover, GASPAR (parameters of the instrument are described in the Deliverable 1.5) was mounted also on the benthic laboratory. The sensor was encapsulated into an aluminum housing (2 mm in thickness), while the LYNX module had its own housing (combination of 6 mm aluminum plates and plastic body). However, technical difficulties with the communication system did not allow us to gather radioactivity data with GASPAR.

Figure 36 - a) GASPAR (blue colored housing) mounted onto the benthic laboratory and b) preparation of the connections of LYNX before the deployment

4.6. αSPECT

Basic operational αSPECT parameters

MCA setup	
channels	256
LLD	5-10
coarse gain	10
fine gain	4
Shaping time	1.0 μs
Flattop	1.2 μs
Input polarity	Negative
Bias voltage	2500
Triggering filter	Pile up, Standard, +1;0;-2;0;+1, 1/16, 400 MHz
IP	10.0.0.10

With these parameters, the 5.5 MeV ²⁴¹Am line is expected near the middle of the spectrum.

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The α SPECT instrument is the most complex instrument of the benthic laboratory considering it consists of a water filtration system, a closed air-extraction loop, and a custom-made radon spectrometer.

In Figure 37 the full connection schematics diagram is presented. Starting with the detector module, it houses essentially 4 parts: The precipitation chamber with the silicon detector, the MCA527, the preamplifier, and its dedicated power supply. The MCA527 supplies the precipitation chamber with the necessary high voltage, which results in the positively charged radon progenies to precipitate onto the detector. The signal generated from the subsequent radon progeny decays is then fed to the preamplifier, powered by an external unit, to avoid ground loops, and the preamplified signal is fed to the MCA for binning. The detector module has two feedthroughs, one for power, and one for ethernet, for the control of the MCA. To complete the instrument, there are two dedicated recirculation loops: The first one pumps sea water through a set of three water filters of gradual particle size filtering to remove unwanted particles. Filtered water, after the gas extraction module is driven back to the sea. The second loop recirculates the gas content that was extracted from the water loop. This gas mixture, transported with the use of an air-pump circulator is guided through a purifier that removes unwanted particles such as CO₂ and humidity, and ultimately guided in the precipitation chamber, where the radon measurement takes place. The air-pump circulator also functions as a purging device to remove the gaseous samples, in order to initiate the next measurement.

Figure 37 - Schematic of the various connections of the full instrument. Black lines indicate electrical connections, red lines indicate gas flow, and blue lines water flow. See text for more details.

The spectrometer arrived on site on 19/10/2024. On the 28th, two additional layers of kapton were placed around the detector module, and the detector system was tested for voltages up to 3.5 kV. This was performed after it was decided the utilization of a 3-hr measurement protocol. For such a duration, the usage of higher precipitation voltages, and corresponding energy consumption, was consumption-wise attainable. Moreover, communications through ethernet were checked, along with the overall response of the instrument. The following day,

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the feedthroughs were placed, the spectrometer module was finalized and added to the benthic laboratory.

Figure 38 - The detector of α SPECT, installed in the benthic laboratory. See text for more details

In Figure 38 the detector of α SPECT is depicted (left) along with gas recirculation and purification system (center).

Figure 39 - Water filtration system. See text for more details.

In Figure 39 the water filtration system is shown. It consists of a three-stage filtering system that filters out in sequence 10, 2.5 and 1 micron in diameter particles.

Figure 40 - The gas separation system

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Figure 41 - The front of the benthic laboratory.

Figure 42 - All the instruments of the RAMONES project deployed

On 30/10/24, during the first underwater deployment in the local port, the instrument was properly connected and tested. High voltage was checked for 4.5 kV and then left at 2 kV. After 2 hours, connectivity was lost and never regained until the end of the 2nd deployment. During disassembly of the benthic lab, it was found that water was introduced within the detector, leading to a major malfunction of the MCA527 unit. The preamp section of the instrument has no visible damage, while its dedicated power supply seems fully destroyed.

5. RAMONES Acoustic Communications Experiments at Palaia Fokaia, Greece

To validate the inverted USBL pinger/replier stack developed by NTUA, as well as the communications with the benthic lab acoustic devices, field tests were conducted together with EvoLogics at Palaia Fokaia, Greece. This inverted USBL stack allows the underwater glider to autonomously estimate its position using acoustic signals, based on relative position estimation with respect to the ASV using USBL positioning, and exploiting GNSS information of the ASV transmitted back to the glider via piggyback messages for achieving geolocalization. The experiments, which included the NTUA glider, the benthic lab modem, and the top-side modem mounted on a small boat, were performed at a site in Palaia Fokaia selected for its accessibility, sufficient depth, and proximity to our NTUA laboratory (Figure 43).

Figure 43 - General (left) and zoomed-in (right) views from the interactive on-line visualisation of the surface vehicle and the glider during the experiments at Palaia Fokaia, Greece.

The tests, described in detail in D2.3, validated the correct operation of the system, both with respect to glider positioning using the inverse USBL stack, and with respect to burst transmission of simulated data from the Benthic Lab and the acoustic release of the platform using the EvoLogics equipment. Images from the field tests are shown in Figure 44.

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Figure 44 - Operations during the experiments of RAMONES acoustic equipment at Palaia Fokaia, Greece.

6. Appendix

RAMONES Final Experiments Draft Work Plan

Kolumbo underwater volcano, Santorini, Greece

Oct – Dec 2024

Robotic Vehicles

6.1. Objectives

- Demonstrate water column radioactivity measurements using autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs).
- Demonstrate Coordination and accurate positioning between AUGs and Sail drone.
- Demonstrate adaptive path planning.

6.2. Dates (proposed)

October 21 – 31, 2024 (+2 days)

6.3. Operation Area

Kolumbo underwater volcano

6.4. Port

Exo Gialos Harbor, 10kn away from Kolumbo.

Facilities

- Ramp for deploying boat/Sail drone.
- Covered barrack for laptop ops (red box), 220V grid supply is available.
- Space for installing tents for extra shade.
- Support from the local fishermen community.
- It is possible to leave the A-Tirma sailboat ASV parked in the water during the night.

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6.5. Storage

[Saint Christodoulos church](#). Big space that is provided for no cost for the project.

It has a big space for vehicle storage and for hardware work if needed.

10 min drive to the Exo Gialos harbor

6.6. Boats

One inflatable type boat, 5-7 m length.

Operated by Partners' personnel

My Crocodile

6.7. Accommodation

We hope to make a deal with [Porto Castello](#). It is next to the port and a perfect place to install the 24/7 ops center.

A second place is also under consideration but is more inland.

6.8. Transportation (in island)

Rental cars plus 1 or 2 cars provided by locals.

6.9. Support equipment

Equipment	Responsible partner	Details/ notes
Hand held GPS	IST?	Garmin 276C
Backup hand help GPS	PLOA	USB GPS
Portable VHF radios	PLOA has 2 units	How many do we need? 2 for console, 2 for 2 boats + 2 backup = 6 is ok?
Generator for emergency power?	NTUA	There is a 6kW generator
Batteries/ Inverter for emergency power?	NTUA - PLOA	There is a 1kW inverter and battery
UPS for critical equipment?	NTUA - PLOA	Radios and 1 or 2 critical laptops. We can use the inverter and

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		charge the battery on the same time
PPEs	PLOA will have 2 The boats should have the legal amount (probably not for working type)	Lifejackets (work fit/ automatic) for all personnel in the boats. Anything else?
Quadrotor drone	NTUA	To capture images of the operations
5G modem and Bullet wi-fi modem	IST	To improve/ backup A-Tirma Wi-Fi/4G PLOA has a 4G data sim card for the ASV
A-Tirma G3 sailboat and support equipment (inverter, tools, etc.)	ROC-SIANI-ULPGC	All equipment in sailboat's transportation crane

6.10. Personnel (please add names or just total numbers)

Partner	Name	Dates	Boat license
PLOATECH	Angelos Mallios	all	Yes
	Othonas Vlassopoulos	all	Yes
	Enrique Fernandez	all	
	Richard Camilli	all	Yes
NTUA	Konstantinos Karantzalos		Yes
	Valsamis Ntouskos	all	
	Christos Antoniou	all	
	Simon Vellas	all	Yes (sailing)
	Sotiris Spanos	all	Yes
EVO	Emanuele Coccolo	all	no
IST-ID	David Cabecinhas	all	Yes
	Luís Sebastião	all	Yes
	Eduardo Cunha	all	Yes
	António Pascoal	All	no
ROC-SIANI-ULPGC	Jorge Cabrera Gámez	all	no
	Antonio C. Domínguez Brito	all	no

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NKUA	Theo Mertzimekis	All	No
	Georgios Siltzovalis	All	No
	Ioannis Madesis	All	No
	Varvara Lagaki	Partial	No

6.11. Operations Scheduling

General plan (draft)

Date	Task	Notes
19 – 20 /10	Mobilization	Partners arriving to Santorini
21 – 27 /10	Testing and preparations	Lab, dock, and short water tests
28 -31 /10	Full scale demonstration	3 days of 24/7 Ops @ Kolumbo
01 – 03 /11	Demobilization	Partners leaving Santorini

24/7 Ops plan (draft)

Shifts: 4 or 6 hours shifts depending on the available personnel.

Minimum shifts Personnel: 1 boat operator, 1 crew, 1 software controller.

Day	Shifts	Boat operator	Boat support	Control station
1	0800 – 1200			
	1200 – 1600			
	1600 – 2000			
	2000 – 2400			
	2400 – 0400			
	0400 – 0800			
2	0800 – 1200			
	1200 – 1600			
	1600 – 2000			
	2000 – 2400			
	2400 – 0400			
	0400 – 0800			
3	0800 – 1200			
	1200 – 1600			
	1600 – 2000			
	2000 – 2400			
	2400 – 0400			
	0400 – 0800			